

Mn^{II} catalyzed oxidation of *p*-phenetidine by periodate ion – A kinetic and mechanistic study

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Abstract : The kinetics of the periodate oxidation of *p*-phenetidine (PEA) in acetone-water medium has been followed by monitoring the increase in the absorbance of reaction intermediate, C₄, and the main reaction product is 4-ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone. Results under pseudo-first order conditions, [IO₄⁻] >> [PEA], are in agreement with the rate law :

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4K_w[Mn^{II}][PEA][IO_4^-]_0[H^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2)[H^+] + K_b[H^+]^2\}$$

where kK_3K_4 is the empirical composite rate constant, K_w is ionic product of water, K_2 is acid dissociation constant of H₄IO₆⁻ and K_b is base dissociation constant of PEA. In agreement with the rate law the $1/k_{cat}$ versus [H⁺] profile passes through the minimum. Free radical scavengers do not affect the reaction rate. The values of thermodynamic parameters are : $\Delta E = 17.94$ kJ mol⁻¹, $A = 5.5 \times 10^{10}$ dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹; $\Delta S^\ddagger = -156.58$ J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹, $\Delta G^\ddagger = 66.55$ kJ mol⁻¹ and $\Delta H^\ddagger = 15.36$ kJ mol⁻¹.

Keywords : Kinetics, Mn^{II} catalysed, periodate oxidation, *p*-phenetidine, 4-ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone.

Introduction

There are some reports available in literature related to the Mn^{II} catalysed/uncatalysed periodate oxidation of aromatic amines¹⁻¹³. The kinetic-mechanistic studies on the Mn^{II} catalysed periodate oxidation of *p*-phenetidine (PEA) in acetone-water medium are being presented in the present communication.

Experimental

Reagents and chemicals :

Sodium metaperiodate (Loba Chemie), *p*-phenetidine (Alfa Aesar), acetone (E. Merck), manganese sulphate monohydrate (Aldrich) and all other chemicals of analytical reagent/guaranteed reagent grade were used after redistillation/recrystallization. Triply distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions. Thiel, Schultz and Koch buffer¹⁴ was used for maintaining the pH.

Kinetic procedure :

The reaction was studied in a spectrophotometric

cell and initiated by adding temperature equilibrated NaIO₄ solution of known concentration to the reaction mixture containing the PEA, Mn^{II} and buffer and maintained at the desired temperature (± 0.1 °C).

The progress of the reaction was followed by recording the absorbance on Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV-2550), at 465 nm, i.e. the λ_{max} at which reaction intermediate/product absorbs. λ_{max} was not found to change with change in time under experimental conditions. Desired temperature was maintained with the help of a high precision thermostatic control.

Product analysis :

Reaction mixture containing 0.015 M NaIO₄ + 0.001 M PEA + 1.456×10^{-7} M Mn^{II} + 5.0% (v/v) acetone, was prepared, shaken and set aside for 24 h. The reaction mixture was extracted with petroleum ether (40–60 °C), the extract was evaporated at room temperature. On separation of a droplet (due to water), a solid residue was left on the watch glass which was found to be TLC single (using 0.5 mm thick plate

of silica gel G and acetone : benzene in the ratio 20 c.c. : 80 c.c. as the eluent; developed for 35 min). This compound was red in colour. The remaining part of filtrate and the moisture droplet were having other reaction products which could not be separated and characterized. The red compound was subjected to different studies. The melting point of this compound was found to be 96.5 °C (Lit. value 96 °C for 4-ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone)¹⁵. This compound gave a positive test for quinone¹⁶. In UV-Vis spectrum, the λ_{\max} obtained for this compound in CHCl_3 solvent were found to be 264 nm, 315 nm and 500 nm which suggest the presence of quinonoid structure in compound. Further this spectrum matches with the one already reported for 4-ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone (Reported values 262, 314 and 496 nm)¹⁵.

The IR spectrum of this compound in KBr, showed the bands at 1635 cm^{-1} (s) (indicating the presence of C=O on 1,4-benzoquinone pattern with the possibility that the position of this band got lowered due to +I effect of methyl group¹⁷⁻¹⁹), 3175 cm^{-1} (s) (may be due to overtones of C=O stretch as the frequency is about twice that of C=O stretch), 2970 cm^{-1} (s) (due to isolated C-H stretching²⁰). Further, the bands at 1393 cm^{-1} and 1492 cm^{-1} (s) may be due to C=C ring stretch, the bands at 1108 cm^{-1} (m) to 1166 cm^{-1} (m) may be due to the in plane C-H bending. The bands were also obtained at 510 and 820 cm^{-1} (m) (due to out of plane C-H bending²⁰). Further, the asymmetric and symmetric C-O-C stretch are shown by the bands at 1245 cm^{-1} (s) and 1045 cm^{-1} (s) respectively.

The melting point, UV-Vis spectrum and IR spectrum recorded for this compound are in good agreement with the values reported in literature for 4-ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone¹⁵. Further, a positive test of quinone^{16,20} and the IR spectrum support the same structure for this compound. Therefore, it should be 4-ethoxy-1,2-benzoquinone with structure given below :

Stoichiometry :

Stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by allowing a known excess of NaIO_4 to react with substrate. After completion of the reaction, the precipitated product was filtered out and in the filtrate unconsumed NaIO_4 was determined iodometrically. The results indicated the stoichiometry to be 1 mol PEA : 2 moles NaIO_4 for the reaction as in eq. (1).

Results

Preliminary observations :

On mixing the reactants, the solution turned light pink, thereafter orange and then violet in colour. On keeping for long time, it finally gives the product. These observations indicate the formation of more than one intermediate prior to the formation of final reaction product. The rapid scan of the violet solution showed the λ_{\max} of the intermediate, C_4 , to be 465 nm

Fig. 1. Rapid UV-Vis scan of reaction solution at different time at pH = 6.5, $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 3.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[p\text{-Phen}] = 8.0 \times 10^{-5}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 1.456 \times 10^{-6}\text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

(Fig. 1). IO₄⁻, PEA and Mn^{II} show no absorption in visible region as indicated by their UV-Vis spectra. Hence, for following the kinetics the absorbance changes were recorded at 465 nm at which only the intermediate C₄ absorbs.

Rate law :

The kinetics was studied under pseudo order conditions by keeping [IO₄⁻] concentration in excess. Guggenheim's method was used for evaluation of pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*_{obs}. Under these conditions, the kinetics was defined by the rate law (2).

$$d[C]/dt = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{PEA}] [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] \quad (2)$$

where *k*_{obs} = *k*_{cat} [IO₄⁻]₀ [Mn^{II}] and *k*_{cat} is the rate constant for Mn^{II} catalysed pathway. [IO₄⁻]₀ and [PEA]₀ represent respectively, the initial concentrations of periodate and PEA out of which former one is

taken in excess. In the absence of Mn^{II}, no significant reaction occurred. The values of *k*_{cat} obtained for different [Mn^{II}], [IO₄⁻]₀ and [PEA] are seen to be in good agreement and consistent with the rate law (2) (Table 1).

Effect of pH, ionic strength, acetone, free radical scavengers and temperature :

The effect of pH was examined in the range 5.0–8.5. 1/*k*_{cat} versus pH plot indicates a maximum at pH 7.0 (Table 1, Fig. 2). An increase in ionic strength, μ, with the help of sodium chloride {(1–4) × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³} led to slight increase in the rate (7.8%) and an increase in the acetone led to a decrease in the rate. Free radical scavengers, viz. acrylamide and allyl alcohol had no effect on the reaction rate.

By determining the rate constants at four different temperatures (30.0 to 45.0 °C), the values of different

Table 1. Effect of variation of concentration of reactants, [Mn^{II}], pH and dielectric constant on the reaction rate
Temp. = 35.0 ± 0.1 °C

[NaIO ₄] × 10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	[PEA] × 10 ⁵ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Mn ^{II}] × 10 ⁷ (mol dm ⁻³)	Acetone × 10 ³ (v/v)%	[NaCl] (mol dm ⁻³)	pH	Temp. ± 0.1 °C	<i>K</i> _{obs} × 10 ³ (s ⁻¹)	<i>K</i> _{cat} × 10 ⁻⁷ (dm ⁶ mol ⁻² s ⁻¹)
50.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	3.97	5.4
60.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	4.97	5.4
70.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	5.50	5.4
80.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	6.00	5.2
90.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	6.52	5.0
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.22	5.0
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.22	5.0
100.0	6.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.49	5.1
100.0	7.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.91	5.4
100.0	8.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	8.10	5.5
100.0	9.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	8.52	5.8
100.0	10.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	8.64	5.9
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.22	5.0
100.0	5.0	2.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	12.49	5.1
100.0	5.0	3.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	17.08	5.0
100.0	5.0	4.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	22.03	5.0
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	5.0	35.0	2.87	2.6
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	5.5	35.0	3.79	3.6
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.0	35.0	5.88	4.2
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.22	5.0
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	7.0	35.0	7.84	5.1
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	7.5	35.0	4.3	4.6

Table 1 (contd.)

100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	8.0	35.0	2.99	3.3
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	8.5	35.0	3.03	2.1
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	1.0	6.5	35.0	7.25	5.1
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	2.0	6.5	35.0	7.51	5.2
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	3.0	6.5	35.0	7.78	5.3
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	4.0	6.5	35.0	8.14	5.5
100.0	5.0	1.456	2.5	–	6.5	35.0	8.52	5.8
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.22	5.0
100.0	5.0	1.456	7.5	–	6.5	35.0	6.08	4.2
100.0	5.0	1.456	10.0	–	6.5	35.0	5.42	3.7
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	30.0	6.43	4.4
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	35.0	7.22	5.0
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	40.0	8.09	5.5
100.0	5.0	1.456	5.0	–	6.5	45.0	9.02	6.1

Fig. 2. ($1/k_{cat}$ (Obsd.) or $1/k_{cat}$ (Calcd.))–pH profile) at $[p\text{-Phen}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{II}] = 1.456 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), temp. = $35 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\lambda_{max} = 465 \text{ nm}$.

thermodynamic parameters were found and these are given in Table 2.

Discussion

Some important features of this reaction are as follows. Firstly, faster colour changes in the reaction mixture relative to the separation of product on standing for long time indicates the formation of the colored intermediate on a time scale of minutes and that of the final product on a time scale of hours. The overall reaction appears to involve several steps and possibly several transient intermediates, in addition to comparatively stable one C_4 . Secondly, the kinetic order of one in periodate against the requirement of two periodate molecules for each PEA molecule in the stoichiometry (eq. (1)) requires the involvement of only one periodate ion in the rate determining step and second IO_4^- ion to be consumed in a fast step leading to

Table 2. Activation parameters for Mn^{II} catalyzed periodate oxidation of 2,5-xylidine in acetone-water medium $[p\text{-Phen}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{II}] = 1.456 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Acetone = 5.0% (v/v), pH = 6.5, $\lambda_{max} = 465 \text{ nm}$

Temp. $\pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$10^{-6} k_{cat}$ ($\text{dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	ΔE (kJ mol^{-1})	$A \times 10^{-10}$ ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})
30.0	4.42					
35.0	4.96					
40.0	5.56	17.94	5.5	156.58	66.55	15.36
45.0	6.19					

the formation of the intermediate, C₄. Since the concentration of C₄ increases continuously with time and reaches a limiting value, its concentration can not be in steady state. Thirdly, 1/k_{cat} versus [H⁺] plot indicates the presence of at least three differently reactive reactant species in the pH region chosen for study. Finally, the observation that free radical scavengers have no effect on reaction rate rules out the involvement of free radicals in the oxidation mechanism.

In aqueous solutions, periodate exists in following equilibria (3–4).

The value of K₁ indicates that in the pH range 5.0–8.5 species H₅IO₆ shall be practically non-existent and hence only species H₄IO₆⁻ and H₃IO₆²⁻ need be considered for explaining observed pH-dependence. In aqueous solution, *p*-phenetidine²¹, undergoes the following acid-base equilibrium with K_b = 1.79 × 10⁻⁹.

Since in the studied pH-range, both C₂H₅OC₆H₄NH₂ and C₂H₅OC₆H₄N⁺H₃ exist, these species have been taken into account. The pH effect may be explained by assuming the C₂H₅OC₆H₄NH₂ and H₄IO₆⁻ to be reactive.

Based on the observed kinetics rate law (eq. (2)) and pH-dependence, the following mechanism is proposed.

In steps (6–9), [C₁], [C₂], [C₃] and [C₄] are intermediates, out of which [C₄] appears to undergo very slow

reorganization/hydrolysis to yield the reaction product, C₅.

In the mechanism for simplicity, H₄IO₆⁻ has been written as IO₄⁻. The formation of intermediates [C₁] and [C₂] in a rapid step having low values of equilibrium constants, K₃ and K₄, is assumed in the proposed gross mechanism. In the detailed mechanism (Scheme 1),

Scheme 1

the catalytic role of Mn²⁺ appears to be due to the formation of a ternary complex, [(PEA)Mn(H₄IO₆)]⁺, in which Mn acts as a conduit for electron transfer.

The proposed mechanism (6–9) leads to the rate law (11).

$$d[\text{C}_4]/dt = kK_3K_4[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}][\text{IO}_4^-] [\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2] \quad (11)$$

On substituting the values of concentrations of the reactive species [C₂H₅OC₆H₄NH₂] and [IO₄⁻] in terms of equilibria (3–4) and (5), respectively, in eq. (2), the complete rate law including [H⁺]-dependence becomes :

$$d[\text{C}]/dt = kK_3K_4[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] \left\{ \frac{[\text{PEA}][\text{OH}^-]}{[\text{OH}^-] + K_b} \right\} \left\{ \frac{[\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{H}^+]}{K_2 + [\text{H}^+]} \right\} \quad (12)$$

On replacing the term, [OH⁻][H⁺], by K_w in numerators

tor, and $[\text{OH}^-]$ by $K_w/[\text{H}^+]$ in denominator, and on rearranging, the eq. (12) becomes eq. (13).

$$d[C]/dt = kK_3K_4[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}]K_w[\text{PEA}][\text{IO}_4^-]_0[\text{H}^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2)[\text{H}^+] + K_b[\text{H}^+]^2\} \quad (13)$$

On comparing eqs. (2) and (13), we get

$$k_{\text{cat}} = kK_3K_4K_w[\text{H}^+]/\{K_2K_w + (K_w + K_bK_2)[\text{H}^+] + K_b[\text{H}^+]^2\} \quad (14)$$

Eq. (14) on rearranging becomes eq. (15).

$$1/k_{\text{cat}} = (K_2/kK_3K_4[\text{H}^+]) + \{(K_w + K_bK_2)/kK_3K_4K_w\} + K_b[\text{H}^+]/kK_3K_4K_w \quad (15)$$

The k_{cat} and pH data were fitted to eq. (15) and the best fit value of composite rate constant kK_3K_4 was found to $4.74 \times 10^7 \text{ dm}^6 \text{ mol}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The plot comprising of the experimental data and calculated data is shown in Fig. 2. In this case, all experimental values are in good agreement and fall on the calculated line which confirms the applicability of eq. (15) in the studied pH range i.e. 5.0–8.5.

The nature of the rate law (15) shows that a plot of $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ shall pass through a minimum^{1,5}. On differentiating $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ with respect to $[\text{H}^+]$ in eq. (15), we get the values of $d^2[1/k_{\text{cat}}]/d[\text{H}^+]^2$. The value of second derivative is found to be positive showing the plot of $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus $[\text{H}^+]$ to pass through a minimum. Thus, on setting $d[1/k_{\text{cat}}]/d[\text{H}^+]$ equal to zero for obtaining hydrogen ion concentration at which the $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ vs $[\text{H}^+]$ profile will pass through minimum, we obtain,

$$[\text{H}^+]_{\text{min}} = (K_2K_w/K_b)^{1/2} \quad (16)$$

On substituting the values of K_2 , K_w and K_b , we get

$$[\text{H}^+]_{\text{min}} = 1.56 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$$

It is noteworthy that the calculated value of $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{min}}$ is in satisfactory agreement with the experimental value of $[\text{H}^+]_{\text{min}}$ of $1.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ obtained from $1/k_{\text{cat}}$ versus pH plot (Fig. 2) and this provides strong support to the proposed mechanism.

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